

Comparison of state of the art sampling-based Bayesian Updating techniques

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Abstract

Nowadays, model updating has an increasing importance in many areas of interest for engineering applications such as structural health monitoring or risk and reliability assessment. As a matter of fact, it allows for solving a plethora of inverse problems with high computational efficiency, allowing for example to monitor structural parameter, to detect damage quickly and to timely intervene with mitigating actions. Among the algorithms available to solve Bayesian updating, methods based on sampling present a flexibility that allows solving the problem numerically, either based on Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method or based on the usage of Bayesian updating with structural reliability (BUS) methods. Additionally, BUS can be coupled with additional methods such as surrogate modelling and efficient simulation methods to further improve its numerical efficiency. Thus, engineering practitioners need to understand which possible combination of the available algorithms should be used to solve their needs. In this paper, we provide an overview of different MCMC and BUS methods, directly calling the model and also employing the Kriging meta-model, covering in detail the advantages and disadvantages of each method as well as their applicability. The investigated methods are applied to solve model updating and model class selection. Two numerical examples are used to verify and test the analysed methods, drawing conclusion on their accuracy, performance, robustness, numerical efficiency and ability to perform model class selection.

Keywords: Bayesian Updating, Model Identification, Markov Chain, Simulation, Kriging

1. Introduction

For many engineering application such as structural health monitoring, damage detection or risk and reliability assessment, it is important to be able to identify unknown parameter of a model and to select the best fitting model out of multiple competing models solely based on measured data [1][2]. These applications usually present inverse problems that need to be dealt with reliably, which is possible by model updating techniques. This work focuses on likelihood-free Bayesian model updating [3], spotlighting two methods based on Markov Chains and two examples based on Bayesian Updating with structural reliability methods. These methods are widely employed and well established because of their potential, their fast and easy implementation and general applicability. Furthermore, they can be easily expanded by using them in combination with meta-modelling techniques or additional reliability methods such as Subset Simulation or Staircase Random Variables [4][5].

At first Bayesian Model Updating and the four methods are introduced. After that an example to show the sampling and convergence behaviour of the methods and a more complex case study to illustrate the accuracy of model class selection as well as the numerical efficiency of the methods are presented and the results discussed.

2. Bayesian Model Updating

In structural health monitoring, the change of system parameters of the structure of interest is observed at different times in order to detect a change early on. This way, timely intervention and repair work can be done, which will decrease maintenance costs and increase the life's expectancy. By using a priori knowledge and the observations of the physical model the unknown uncertain epistemic parameters of the system can be estimated with model updating [1]. This can be achieved with multiple methods that are based

on Bayes' theorem [6]

$$P(A | B) = \frac{P(B | A) \cdot P(A)}{P(B)}, \quad (1)$$

one of the most important equations in probability theory. In the case of sampling based methods, eq. 1 can be written as

$$f(\theta | \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{D}) = \frac{f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta) \cdot f(\theta | \mathcal{M})}{f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M})}, \quad (2)$$

with the posterior probability density function (PDF) $P(A | B) = f(\theta | \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{D})$ of the parameter vector θ , the likelihood $P(B | A) = f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta)$ and the prior PDF $P(A) = f(\theta | \mathcal{M})$. The evidence $P(B) = f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M})$ of the probabilistic model class \mathcal{M} is the normalisation factor to ensure the posterior PDF integrates to 1 and is conditioned on the measured data \mathcal{D} [1][7]. Because of that, the evidence is only dependent on the model. As such it is constant over the model updating process and a higher evidence indicates a better match of the digital model and the physical model. This property allows to select the best fitting model out of a class of models. This is called model class selection and is another key element in the Bayesian statistical framework [3].

The level of agreement between the numerical model output and the observed data is described by the likelihood. The likelihood contains the mechanical model and is therefore able to relate the observations to the model parameters [4] but needs to be evaluated at every measured input point. Oftentimes, this is computationally prohibitive as well as analytically unavailable [3]. Instead of directly evaluating the likelihood, a numerical sampling approach can be used. In this case, a dataset from the proposed parameters is created and its proximity to the observed dataset is compared. This concept is called the likelihood-free approach [3].

In this work the comparison of the two datasets is performed based on Euclidean distance, however, it is pointed out, that different metrics can be employed as well, such as

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the Bhattacharyya distance, which is able to compare the statistical properties of the datasets [5]. In the following four Bayesian Updating methods are presented in more detail.

2.1. Transitional Markov Chain Monte Carlo Method

One family of methods is based on Markov Chain Monte Carlo Method (MCMC), introduced by [8]. This method follows two steps: first, it generate samples by standard Monte Carlo Sampling from the prior distribution; secondly, samples are generated from the unknown posterior utilising the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. Even if this algorithm is of simple understanding and implementation, MCMC shows limited capabilities and numerical difficulties to handle sampling from a posterior with a difficult shape, such as very peaked, flat or in higher dimensions. Furthermore, long burn-in periods are sometimes necessary, impacting the efficiency and validity of the algorithm negatively.

In order to solve these problems, Ching and Chen [7] developed the Transitional Markov Chain Monte Carlo (TMCMC) method, motivated by the adaptive Metropolis-Hastings algorithm [9]. Instead of directly sampling from a difficult posterior PDF, a series of intermediate PDFs

$$f_j(\theta) \propto f(\theta | \mathcal{M}) \cdot f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta)^{p_j} \quad (3)$$

$$j = 0, \dots, m \quad 0 = p_0 < p_1 < \dots < p_m = 1$$

with j denoting the stage number, is introduced that converges to the target PDF. By down-scaling the contribution of the likelihood by the exponent p_j , the change between the p_j 's and the p_{j+1} 's intermediate PDF will be small enough to enable efficient sampling. The choice of p_{j+1} can have a large effect on the performance and should neither be too small nor too large, and it is adaptively chosen, so that the coefficient of variation (COV) of the likelihood $f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta)$ is equal to an prescribed threshold [7]. A reasonable choice for the COV is usually of 100 %.

For many problems, the main support region of the prior PDF does not match the high likelihood region of the posterior PDF, which leads to large variances and low acceptance rates [7]. The TMCMC algorithm employs therefore the logarithm of the likelihood, the so-called loglikelihood, instead of the likelihood to avoid this issue. Another advantage is, that the loglikelihood is better suited for difficult PDFs because small changes in the likelihood can be better detected. The burn-in period is also of no concern anymore.

The TMCMC algorithm consists of two stages. In the first stage, samples are generated from the prior PDF by direct Monte Carlo simulation. They are therefore able to cover the whole range of the prior PDF and are widely spread. In the second stage, resampling and weighting of the samples is performed for the m intermediate stages until $p_j = 1$. The plausibility weights of the samples can be calculated

by

$$w(\theta_{j,k}) = \frac{f(\theta_{j,k} | \mathcal{M}) \cdot f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta_{j,k})^{p_{j+1}}}{f(\theta_{j,k} | \mathcal{M}) \cdot f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta_{j,k})^{p_j}} \quad (4)$$

$$= f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta_{j,k})^{p_{j+1}-p_j}$$

with $k = 1, \dots, N_j$. Following that, the asymptotically unbiased estimator

$$S_j = \sum_{k=1}^{N_j} \frac{w(\theta_{j,k})}{N_j} \quad (5)$$

for the expected value of the plausibility weights

$$E[w(\theta_{j,k})] = \int w(\theta) \cdot f_j(\theta) d\theta$$

$$= \frac{\int f(\theta | \mathcal{M}) \cdot f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta)^{p_{j+1}} d\theta}{\int f(\theta | \mathcal{M}) \cdot f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta)^{p_j} d\theta} \quad (6)$$

is calculated.

The resampling step is started by initialising N_j Markov chains from the prior samples. For $k = 1, \dots, N_{j+1}$ Metropolis-Hastings is performed with a stationary PDF to obtain the new samples

$$\theta_{j+1,k} = \theta_{j,l} \quad \text{with probability} \quad \frac{w(\theta_{j,l})}{\sum_{l=1}^{N_j} w(\theta_{j,l})} \quad (7)$$

l is a dummy index and the probability denotes the new probability distribution. Lastly, in order to perform the model class selection, the asymptotically unbiased estimator for the evidence \mathcal{M}

$$S \equiv \prod_{j=0}^{m-1} S_j \quad (8)$$

is computed.

2.2. Transitional Markov Chain Monte Carlo with adaptive Kriging meta-modelling

Given both the sequential sampling and iterative nature of TMCMC, the computational cost of such algorithm can quickly become prohibitive, especially if an the evaluation of a complex numerical model is required for the computaiton of the likelihood. TMCMC can be coupled with Kriging meta-modelling in order to reduce the computational costs substantially. This is achieved because the model is evaluated explicitly only for few samples, which are used to train a meta-model that allows for approximate but fast interpolating estimates. The samples are no longer generated from the model itself but from the meta-model, which reduces the number of full model evaluations significantly. The here presented Kriging meta-modelling techniques for TMCMC, K-TMCMC, was developed by Angelikopoulos et al. [10].

Let there be m support points $[\theta_1, \theta_m]$ in the parameter space for which the full model simulation is available, and let $\mathbf{Y} = [J(\theta_1), \dots, J(\theta_m)]^T$ be the available values for the

fit function $J(\theta_i)$. The fit function is a weight that expresses the proximity between the measured data and the model predictions. It is expressed through Kriging interpolation for a new point θ by

$$J(\theta) = \mathbf{Q}^T(\theta)\beta + \varepsilon(\theta) \quad (9)$$

with the basis functions $\mathbf{Q}^T(\theta) = [\mathbf{Q}_1(\theta), \dots, \mathbf{Q}_m(\theta)]$ and the regression coefficients $\beta = [\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m]^T$. $\varepsilon(\theta)$ is a zero mean stochastic process with variance σ^2 and covariance $C_\varepsilon = \sigma^2 R(\varphi; \theta, \theta')$. φ is a set of parameters with points in the parameter space θ and θ' . The choice of the correlation function $R(\cdot)$ critically influences on how Kriging presents the data.

The prediction at point θ is estimated using

$$\hat{J}(\theta) = \mathbf{Q}^T(\theta)\hat{\beta} + \mathbf{r}^T \hat{R}^{-1} (\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{Q}\hat{\beta}) \quad (10)$$

with \mathbf{r} with $r_i = R(\hat{\varphi}, \hat{\alpha}; \theta_j, \theta)$ and $\hat{R} = R(\hat{\varphi}, \hat{\alpha})$. Similar to Angelikopoulos, the Kriging package *DACE* is used as well [10].

The Kriging model is trained by keeping the samples from the old stage and adding new samples with each step. The algorithm is local and adaptive by using samples in the near vicinity to estimate a new sample. Techniques to control the error introduced to the Kriging prediction are explained in more detail in [10]. Here only the user-specified tolerance value ε is pointed out. ε is used to determine whether a full model evaluation is necessary or not and has therefore a large impact on the performance of the algorithm, as it affects bias reduction and convergence speed.

2.3. Bayesian Updating with Structural Reliability Methods

BUS enhances the rejection sampling, which generates exact and uncorrelated samples of the posterior and is also straight forward to implement. By adding an additional uniformly distributed random variable to the space of random variables, the model updating problem is instead expressed as a structural reliability problem in the augmented random variable space [11]. BUS-based methods can easily be coupled with other structural reliability methods, which allows for further variation and improvement as well as adjustment to the problem at hand.

In BUS initial samples are generated by Monte Carlo sampling from a prior PDF, which is often chosen from a set of standard distributions. Following that, candidate samples are accepted or rejected. At first $U \sim U[0, 1]$ and θ' from the prior PDF $f(\theta | \mathcal{M})$ are generated. If

$$U < cf(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta), \quad (11)$$

the candidate sample θ' is accepted. c is the so-called likelihood multiplier, a constant scalar for which the inequality

$$cf(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta) \leq 1 \quad \forall \theta \quad (12)$$

has to hold. The failure probability is obtained by

$$P_F = \iint f(\theta | \mathcal{M}) I(0 \leq u \leq 1) \quad (13)$$

$$I(u < cf(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}, \theta)) dud\theta \quad (14)$$

and the evidence [11] by

$$f(\mathcal{D} | \mathcal{M}) = c^{-1} \cdot P_F. \quad (15)$$

The choice of the likelihood multiplier is essential, as it is directly proportional to the acceptance rate. As such, it should be chosen as large as possible without introducing bias by violating the inequality eq. 12. The multiplier has to be chosen as an initial parameter, so before the maximal likelihood is known. In BUS c is often set to 1, which is on the safe side but less efficient. Another possibility is to choose c adaptively, as done by adaptive BUS, aBUS [12] or to have a driving variable that is independent from c as proposed by F. A. DiazDelaO [2], called CBUS. Both methods use the logarithm of the likelihood instead of the likelihood. In CBUS, the multiplier only affects the target threshold level $b = -\ln c$. This introduces an outer loop Subset Simulation, which ensures, that the minimal value of b and thus the desirable c_{max} has been reached before stopping the algorithm. Tab. 1 summarises the main differences between the BUS and CBUS formulation. While in BUS the samples are directly conditional on $Y > 0$, a resampling step is necessary. However, in CBUS, the posterior samples are collected from the samples that were generated during Subset Simulation, so resampling is not needed. Another significant difference is, that the loglikelihood is used instead of the likelihood.

Table 1. Comparison of BUS and CBUS.[2]

	BUS	CBUS
Driving variable	$Y = c\mathcal{L}(\theta) - U$ for any $c < [\max_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta)]^{-1}$	$Y = \ln[\mathcal{L}(\theta)/U]$
Target failure event	$F = \{Y > 0\}$	$F = \{Y > b\}$ for any $b > \ln[\max_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta)]$
Evidence calculation	$f(\mathcal{D} \mathcal{M}) = c^{-1} P(Y > 0)$	$P_{\mathcal{D}} = e^b P(Y > 0)$
Stopping criterion	$b_{level} \searrow 0$ Threshold value of simulation level equal to zero	$a_k \searrow 0$ Algorithm determines threshold b_{min} has been crossed

3. Case Study

Two case studies were conducted to compare the different methods with each other. In order to examine the efficiency of sampling and the efficiency in convergence, an example with a known likelihood function and therefore with an available analytical solution is presented. BUS, CBUS and TMCMC are compared with each other in increasing dimensions. Furthermore, model class selection, which is performed by evaluating the evidence, is important for engineering applications as well. The second example therefore examines the accuracy of the evidence and compares the numerical efficiency of CBUS, TMCMC and K-TMCMC.

3.1. System with two mixed Gaussians

In order to examine the efficiency of the sampling and the efficiency in convergence, an example with available analytical solution is presented. The example, that was first introduced in [7], has a known likelihood function, given by a mixture of two Gaussian functions centred at $[0.5 \dots 0.5]$ and $[-0.5 \dots -0.5]$ with standard deviations of $\sigma = 0.1$. Three different methods, BUS, CBUS and TMCMC, are compared in this case study. Another advantage of the chosen example is that the dimension can be chosen arbitrary. The efficiency and robustness of the three examined methods can therefore be well estimated. Here, the dimensions 2, 6 and 10 were chosen. The efficiency of the sampling and in convergence is estimated by comparing the mean and standard deviation of the sampled posterior distribution with the analytical posterior distribution. Another factor, to determine if the chosen algorithms are able to represent the posterior distribution accurately, is the distribution of the samples in the two cluster. Ideally, 50 % of the samples should be in each cluster.

Model updating was performed 50 times for each method and each dimension for $N_{samples} = 2000$ samples per stage.

3.2. Water Distribution Network

Contamination of water distribution networks poses a risk to the performance and safety of the water and thus the public as well [13]. Therefore the identification and characterisation of the contamination source is of great importance [14]. This can be achieved by using monitoring data such as the change of concentration over time at certain control points and available system knowledge. Having sensors installed at certain control points allows to quickly confirm and identify the contaminant event, so that an effective warning system can be employed. To achieve this, the optimal sensor placement is important as well [15]. There are multiple factors that are important to know in order to characterise the contaminant event and its lingering effects. They are the location of the contaminant source, the magnitude of the mass inflow, the injection starting time and the duration. Out of those, the location is the most important factor because it allows for fast corrective actions. Therefore, a fast and reliable identification is crucial [15].

The mass inflow, the injection starting time and also the duration of the contaminant inflow can be estimated with Bayesian model updating. With model class selection, the most likely location of injection can be estimated. This is the second important use for the presented methods.

The model creation and calculation was performed with the hydraulic simulation programme EPANET 2.2 developed by EPA, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, an open source software to model drinking water distribution systems [16]. In this study, the example network 3 is used as the network model [15]. The network will be solved by the internal software with a Lagrangian time-based approach.

Figure 1. Normalised demand pattern for network 3. [15]

Mass conservation is assumed at the nodes and energy conservation at the network links. The network consists of 92 nodes, 117 pipes, two reservoirs, two pumps and three fully mixed tanks. Each node represents a possible injection point, so that there are a total of $N_c = 92$ models to evaluate and to determine the most likely event from. The simulation period covers 24 h in 5 min steps. 5 sensors measure the contaminant concentration during the time interval also every 5 minutes. The corresponding demand pattern is shown in figure 1. For more detail about the network, please refer to [15].

Two different events are examined. Their core information is summarised in table 2. The recorded contaminant concentration is shown in figure 2 for event 1 and figure 3 for event 2. The examined methods are CBUS, TMCMC and TMCMC with Kriging meta-modelling, K-TMCMC.

Table 2. Attributes of the two contaminant events.

	Event 1	Event 2
Source node	101	157
Intensity I [kg/min]	0.2	0.2
Starting Time T [h]	2.0	5.0

Figure 2. Measurement of nodal concentration over time recorded by the 5 sensors. Event 1 [15]

The computation was performed with $N_{samples} = 1000$ samples per stage and an uniform prior distribution. For event one, the prior was defined over $I_i \in [0, 1]$ kg/min and $T_i \in [0, 180]$ min and for event two over $I_i \in [0, 1]$ kg/min and $T_i \in [0, 435]$ min. The upper limit of the time corresponds to the time that two of the five sensors detected the contaminant for the first time. Four different cases were considered for the evaluation of the methods, without uncertainties, with aleatory and epistemic uncertainties, coupled with either considering the full stimulation time or a reduced time, only up to 1 h after arrival of the

Figure 3. Measurement of nodal concentration over time recorded by the 5 sensors. Event 2 [15]

contaminant to two sensors. In the next section only the results for the cases that yielded the best and worst results respectively discussed.

4. Results

In fig. 4 to fig. 6 a representative distribution of the posterior samples of the first example is displayed. In 2 dimension, the samples are mostly evenly distributed in the two distributions, although less so for CBUS. With increasing dimension, the random initial samples are more significant for the final distribution. Because of that they there is a clearly visible tendency to be majorly focused on only one distribution.

Figure 4. Representative sample distributions for example 1 (left) and the respective distribution in cluster (right); $ndim = 2$.

This effect is enhanced by the instances in which the algorithms only identified one of the two Gaussian distributions, which is shown in Tab. 3. TMCM and CBUS have a similar performance, which decreases in higher dimension notably

Figure 5. Representative sample distributions for example 1 (left) and the respective sample-to-cluster-distribution (right); $ndim = 6$.

Figure 6. Representative sample distributions for example 1 (left) and the respective sample-to-cluster-distribution (right); $ndim = 10$.

less than that of BUS, for which its overall performance is significantly worse. It is pointed out, that the BUS algorithm identified both Gaussian function in only 8 % of the runs in 10 dimension.

The samples are further spread for BUS with increasing dimension, which is also notable through the increased standard deviation, clearly visible in fig. 8. The case displayed in fig. 6c, that the TMCMC algorithm identified both Gaussian distributions but the samples do not cover the full domain appropriately, happened regularly. In multiple of these occasions a similar cut in the sample distribution could be seen.

Table 3. Overview on how often only one Gaussian distribution was identified.

	Dim.	Identify only cluster		
		1	2	Σ
BUS	2	0 %	0 %	0 %
	6	48 %	18 %	66 %
	10	52 %	40 %	92 %
CBUS	2	0 %	0 %	0 %
	6	12 %	12 %	24 %
	10	16 %	18 %	34 %
TMCMC	2	0 %	0 %	0 %
	6	0 %	0 %	0 %
	10	16 %	18 %	34 %

All methods were able to describe the statistical properties relatively well. The average mean of each method, shown in fig. 7 for the bottom left Gaussian function, is located in the vicinity of the actual mean. It is pointed out, that the averaged mean of CBUS even for 10 dimension is very close to the actual mean.

Fig. 8 shows the average standard deviation of the three methods in 2, 6 and 10 dimension. The posterior distribution estimated by TMCMC matches the analytical solution quite well while CBUS underestimates the standard deviation. For TMCMC as well as for CBUS, the increased dimension did not have a notable effect on the standard deviation. While the BUS algorithm overestimates the standard deviation already in 2 dimension, it becomes increasingly worse in higher dimension, which is also clearly visible in fig. 4a, fig. 5a and fig. 6a.

As expected, the number of model calls and the computation time increase exponentially with increasing dimension. Fig. 9 shows the average number of model calls and computation time over the dimension as well as the respective minimum and maximum. While all methods show similar efficiency in 2 dimension, large differences become apparent with increasing dimension. The two BUS methods show largely varying results in between two runs, while the performance of TMCMC is more stable with a slower increase. TMCMC is the most efficient method in this application but while the number of model calls is notably higher with CBUS, the computation time is not.

Figure 7. Mean of the sampled posterior distribution for the Gaussian distribution in the 3rd quadrant.

Figure 8. Standard deviation of the sampled posterior distribution. Dashed line represents the analytical standard deviation.

With the results presented above, it is clearly visible, that for 10 dimension the BUS algorithm does not converge adequately anymore. However, CBUS and TMCMC still perform adequately, with CBUS showing slightly better results in the overall distribution of samples and replicating the underlying distribution. It can be seen, that using the loglikelihood instead of the likelihood has a significant positive effect on the usability of the method, not only in efficiency but more so in the convergence behaviour.

For the second example, the methods TMCMC, K-TMCMC and CBUS were compared with each other. The advantage of Kriging meta-modelling, which lies in sampling from the trained meta-model instead of the full model, is visible in Tab. 4 by a significant decrease in

Figure 9. Average number of model calls and average computation time over 50 computations. The minimal and maximal value are displayed in the respectively lighter colour.

Table 4. Computation time and no. model calls for event 1, case 1: full simulation time, no uncertainty.

	TMCMC	K-TMCMC	CBUS
No. model calls	8600	1437	4300
Comp. time [min]	118	21	76

number of full model evaluation and thus a major decrease in computation time.

For the water distribution network example, the focus lies on the model class selection. While 8 different situations were computed, only the best and the worst case are shown here. They are namely the event 1 with full simulation time without considering any uncertainties and event 2, considering only the simulation time up until 1 h after the contaminant has arrived to two sensors as well as taking into account aleatory and epistemic uncertainties. The results of the model class selection of those events are displayed in tab. 5. For event 1, most of the time one node was distinctively selected, with a second node as an alternative possibility. For event 2 however, CBUS was not able to select one model clearly. While one model had the highest evidence and was therefore most likely, a total of 10 models was selected to be probable. Out of these 10 models, the least likely had a normalised evidence of 0.973.

Table 5. By model class selection selected nodes for event 1, full simulation time and without uncertainties and for event 2, reduced simulation time, full uncertainties. Node in bold had the maximum evidence, other nodes a smaller but very similar evidence.

	Event 1	Event 2
CBUS	101 10	195 157, 159, 169, ...
TMCMC	101	195
K-TMCMC	171 179, 101, 103	199

The water distribution network with all selected nodes for both events, each with the aforementioned 4 cases are shown in fig. 10 for event 1 and fig. 11 for event 2. The node 157 in which the contaminant is inserted in event 2 is in the middle of the network and much more difficult to estimate than node 101 from event 1. This is visible in the results of the model class selection as well, as CBUS and TMCMC both selected node 195 downstream of the insertion node. K-TMCMC selected a node further away, which is largely caused by computation problems. Fig. 12 shows, that for the presented case of event 2, many of the node in the middle could not be successfully computed. Therefore the computable node closest to the insertion point was selected. It is assumed, that it is possible to properly compute every node after the Kriging model is well adjusted to the network. Also the CBUS algorithm was not able to conduct model updating at every node, as displayed in fig. 13. It is notable, that in this case, the problematic nodes were on the

Figure 10. Water distribution network with selected nodes for event 1. Circled node is the insertion point, orange nodes were selected as the most likely nodes and yellow as also highly likely nodes.

Figure 11. Water distribution network with selected nodes for event 2. Circled node is the insertion point, orange nodes were selected as the most likely nodes and yellow as also highly likely nodes.

corner of the network without many connecting pipelines. This might point to a larger general problem that is not as easily solvable.

One possible reason for the problems of the CBUS algorithm are the reduced unique samples. In the case rejecting a sample, the previous sample is used instead of the candidate sample. For a problem with a low acceptance rate and a large number of iterations, this can lead to a very small number of unique samples.

5. Conclusion

CBUS and TMCMC are well applicable even in higher dimension. Their efficiency was comparable and the results converged well to the analytical solution. CBUS presented a slightly better sampling behaviour. However, it is possible for difficult problems that the increasingly less unique samples generated with CBUS have a negative effect on the algorithm performance. Furthermore, it cannot be ruled out, that the problems while computing the

Figure 12. Network map with the selected node (green) and nodes that could not be calculated (blue) for event 2 with full uncertainties and considering only the time up to 1h after the arrival of the contamination to two sensors. Results of K-TMCMC. Node 157 is circled

Figure 13. Network map with the selected node (green) and nodes that could not be calculated (blue) for event 2 with full uncertainties and considering only the time up to 1h after the arrival of the contamination to two sensors. Results of CBUS. Node 157 is circled

second example, point towards the limits of this method. The limitation of using the likelihood instead of the loglikelihood became apparent considering the behaviour of BUS in higher dimension and the fact, that it could not be applied to the water distribution network example. K-TMCMC showed well the advantages of employing meta-modelling, namely the highly increased computational efficiency. On the downside, the method is more complex to implement and parameters have to be adjusted to specific problems to achieve the best performance. Previously, Kriging meta-modelling has also been applied to BUS-based methods, such as AK-BUS, BUS with adaptive Kriging meta-modelling, which needs an exceptionally low number of full model evaluations to build the training samples. TMCMC-based and BUS-based methods have a large potential and their usability to various problems could be shown. Further enhancement such as L-TMCMC, with Langevin extension or aBUS, can be employed to improve the performance even more.

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